

ISic0039

I.Sicily inscription 0039

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]pont[---]

2. [---]me[---]

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644806

EDR 137596

EDCS 64800036

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*.
Palermo. At 40

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0039. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4333863>